

**FRAMEWORK FOR EXAMINING THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA
CONTENT ON CONSUMER ENGAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL MARKETING
LANDSCAPE**

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ABSTRACT

Purpose

In recent years, businesses have increasingly used influencer endorsements, also known as influencer marketing, to promote their content through Key Opinion Leaders. The rising prevalence of social media endorsements has made it necessary to comprehend the effects of social media influencers and their product endorsements on buyers. The objective of this study is to analyse how social media content and its qualities affect consumer engagement in the digital environment and to provide some useful frameworks for future research on the subject.

Design/Methodology/Approach

The paper reviews prior literature on influence of social media, social media influence, content - quality, design, characteristics and digital customer engagement, which is one of the main areas of study of the following authors...Berger, J., & Milkman, K. L. (2012), Schultz and Peltier (2013), Chung, N., Han, H., & Koo, C. (2015), Shan, Y., Chen, K. J., & Lin, J. S. (2020), Yan Shan, Kuan-Ju Chen & Jhih-Syuan (Elaine) Lin (2020), Cheung, M. L., Leung, W. K., Aw, E. C. X., & Koay, K. Y. (2022), Teresa Fernandes, Heather Nettleship, Luísa Helena Pinto(2022), Schivinski, B., Pontes, N., Czarnicka, B., Mao, W., De Vita, J., & Stavropoulos, V. (2022), Doyle, J. P., Su, Y., & Kunkel, T. (2022), Davcik, N. S., Langaro, D., Jevons, C., & Nascimento, R. (2022),

Findings

Although a considerable amount of research has been conducted on Social media Influence, social media content since early 2000, but only a few studies only emphasised on content, loyalty, user generated content, customer engagement based on customer online product reviews.

In-depth research on the factors of customer interaction with luxury brands and content relevancy are still lacking (Bazi, S., Filieri, R., & Gorton, M. (2020). As a result, consumer interaction research is frequently mislabelled, making it difficult for academicians and practitioners to keep up with innovations in this field.

Originality/Value

The insights derived from this conceptual review paper can help social media influencers to choose appropriate content and engage their customers in the digital landscape. This paper provides a few frameworks for enthusiast researchers to explore and gain new findings in social media and content engagement. Overall, it will also be helpful to academicians, research scholars and marketing professionals to recognize key characteristics and trends of social media influencer marketing, and thus, drive new insights into social media influencers across different demographic profiles.

Key Words

Social media influence, social media platforms, social media - costs and metrics, Customer reviews, Customer experience, Content research variables like – characteristics, value, effectiveness, information, effectiveness, cost, appeal, design, structure, user generated content and customer engagement

Paper Type: Conceptual

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE DIGITAL LANDSCAPE

Gaining a deep understanding of the cognitive processes of consumers is absolutely essential in today's competitive market. By delving into the intricate workings of their minds, we can uncover invaluable insights into the underlying factors that drive their engagement with brand-specific content. This knowledge empowers us to create compelling and impactful strategies that resonate with our target audience, ultimately leading to increased brand loyalty and sales. Discover the power of advanced digital marketing strategies that not only offer cost-effective solutions but also have a profound impact on the ever-evolving business landscape.

From a strategic standpoint, it is crucial to recognise the significance of pinpointing the exact social media channels that resonate with a company's desired consumer base. This meticulous approach plays a pivotal role in guaranteeing the triumph of digital marketing initiatives. In today's digital landscape, assessing the efficacy of internet marketing strategies across diverse industries has become increasingly crucial. In order to maximise the potential of this study, it is imperative to explore the various internet marketing tactics that can be customised to meet the specific requirements of diverse businesses.

1.1 The Indian Digital Marketing Scenario

According to the global overview report, there were 1.42 billion people living in India as of January 2023, with 692.0 million using the internet (for a penetration rate of 48.7%).

There were 467 million individuals (32.8 percent) using social media in India in January 2023. With 314.6 million members, Facebook's ad reach in India was equivalent to 22.1% of the population. YouTube had 467.0 million users at the time, and 32.8 percent of the population was shown adverts. Advertisements on Instagram, which has 229.6 million active users per month, were seen by 16.1% of the world's population. The 117.6 million persons who saw these ads represent 8.3 percent of the world's population. According to LinkedIn's advertising data, the Indian population made up 7.0% of the 99 million "members" on the platform. With 172.5 million users, Snapchat's ad reach was 12.1% of the global population. While Snapchat, Facebook, and Instagram all have minimum age requirements of 13, LinkedIn requires users to be 18 or older. – Source (www.datareportal.com)

1.2 The Evolution of Consumer Engagement in the Digital Era

Consumers' experiences with companies and their decisions to buy have been profoundly altered by the rise of new digital platforms and shifting consumer behaviours. In the past, marketers could only reach their target audiences through more conventional means, including television, radio, and print media. Social media content is an increasingly important tool for attracting new customers, keeping existing ones happy, and facilitating meaningful interactions with businesses since the advent of the internet and the widespread adoption of smartphones.

1.3 The myriad dimensions of the ever-evolving digital landscape

In today's marketing scene, where the digital domain reigns supreme, social media content has developed as a strong force with significant sway over customer engagement. Without a question, it is influencing how businesses interact with their target audience. The material published on social media platforms is one of the primary causes driving this transition. Social media content has evolved as a powerful tool for marketers to interact with customers, establish brand loyalty, increase conversions, engage customers who will become devoted to the company's products and services, and ultimately become advocates. As a critical component of digital marketing strategy, social media content bridges the gap between businesses and their target consumers in previously imagined ways. This article delves deep into the multifaceted relationship between social media content and consumer engagement, shedding light on its profound implications for businesses.

1.3.1. Customization and Relevance dimension

This refers to tailoring marketing efforts to individual consumers and ensuring that the content and messaging are highly relevant to their specific needs and preferences. By personalising marketing campaigns, businesses

In today's dynamic marketplace, the discerning consumer is faced with an overwhelming influx of information originating from a multitude of diverse sources. Amidst the overwhelming abundance of content, it is evident that personalization and relevance play pivotal roles in shaping consumer engagement. Social media platforms provide businesses with the opportunity to customise content based on specific demographics, interests, and behaviours, resulting in a more targeted approach to reaching consumers and delivering content that aligns with their preferences. The provision of personalised content has the potential to cultivate a

heightened sense of connection and engagement among consumers, as it conveys an understanding and responsiveness to their individual needs and preferences.

1.3.2. Visual Storytelling dimension: Creating Remarkable Narratives

Visual storytelling may be effective in today's fast-paced digital market, when customers' attention spans are short.

Images and films that transmit ideas and stories have become more popular on social media platforms. In general, consumers are more invested in brands whose creators can tell interesting visual tales.

Visual information is easier to remember and spread. It aids in communicating tales, ideals, and feelings in a manner that words alone can't. In order to make an indelible impression on customers and spark meaningful interactions, visual storytelling is frequently used in effective digital marketing campaigns.

A visually compelling narrative has all the makings of a viral sensation. In a flash, it may communicate intricate concepts or stir up intense feelings.

1.3.3. User-Generated Content dimension (UGC): Putting Authenticity to Use

In today's digital landscape, authenticity has become an invaluable and highly sought-after attribute. In today's highly competitive market, it is crucial for brands to establish an authentic and relatable image in order to attract and retain consumers. The modern consumer is savvy and discerning, seeking out brands that they can connect with on a deeper level. By embodying genuineness and relatability, brands can effectively capture the attention and loyalty of their target audience. User-generated content (UGC) is an incredibly powerful tool when it comes to digital marketing. When consumers take the initiative to share their experiences with a brand on various social media platforms, it effectively serves as genuine social proof. User-generated content (UGC) is an incredibly powerful tool in the realm of digital marketing. By featuring authentic individuals utilising genuine products or services, UGC establishes a profound sense of trust and credibility.

By implementing strategies that inspire and empower consumers to generate and distribute content centred around a brand, we can cultivate a vibrant community and foster unwavering loyalty. Contests, hashtags, and challenges have emerged as highly effective strategies to engage users and encourage the creation of user-generated content (UGC). When consumers have the pleasure of witnessing their content being showcased or recognised by a brand, it not only amplifies their level of interaction but also fortifies their emotional bond with the brand.

1.3.4. Influencer Marketing dimension: Harnessing the Power of Credibility

Within the dynamic landscape of social media, influencers have undeniably risen to prominence as a formidable entity that demands our attention and consideration. These individuals have successfully built loyal and engaged audiences through their exceptional expertise, magnetic charisma, and relatable personalities. As a digital marketing manager, it is imperative to acknowledge the immense potential that influencers possess in terms of shaping consumer perceptions and fostering meaningful engagement.

Influencer marketing is a strategic approach that entails partnering with prominent social media personalities to effectively endorse and amplify the reach of products or services. Influencers possess the remarkable ability to curate compelling content that deeply resonates with their dedicated followers. This harmonious alignment between influencers and their audience

frequently results in a significant boost in consumer engagement. In order to maintain authentic brand values whose values align with the impact of the audience they can

Estimating Cost of Airtime = Digital Ad Spend v/s Conversion Ratio

Let's assume an **example** of airing a digital commercial advt. for 6 seconds before ICC World cup finals. Now the cost of airing ranges between ₹ 6 lakhs to ₹ 25 lakhs per a 6 seconds advt. If there are about 30 crore viewers to this advt., what would be the ad spend, estimated profit for a specified cost of the product/service?

Out of 30 crores lets take a .01% response rate, which equals to 3 lakhs viewers who will pay attention to the ad contents. Again, of which let's assume, .01% of these viewers (say 3000 people) have decided to buy the product with a minimum spending per ticket say ₹ 500, then the total estimated revenue generated would be working out to be

3,000 people X ₹ 500 per product cost = ₹ 15,00,000 lakhs revenue.

Spending = ₹ 6 - ₹ 25 Lakhs vis-à-vis revenues ...the digital metrics would allow the advertiser to optimally spend on the specific platform to ensure targeted sales revenues

NOTE: The digital metric Softwares available in the market enable company brand or store managers to exactly measure the precise sales revenues for their product/ service – unit or rupee value, based on the algorithm on which the forecasting was done, social media platforms available, chosen, airtime purchased, customer's details etc., and many more complex calculations at the touch of a button.

Source: Authors data

The primary performance indicators encompass engagement metrics such as likes, shares, comments, click-through rates, and conversion rates. These metrics not only provide valuable insights into the level of engagement but also offer valuable data on the specific types of content that resonate most effectively with our target audience. Utilising advanced analytics tools empowers businesses to effectively segment their audience, enabling them to fine-tune their content strategies to cater to specific demographics.

1.3.7. The dimension of Algorithm

Algorithms are used by social media sites to choose what people see. Algorithms take into account user activity, content relevancy, and past interactions to create a customised feed. If you want your social media posts to get the most exposure possible, you need to have a firm grasp on how these algorithms function.

Likes and shares are two examples of engagement indicators that may help make content more visible. The likelihood of content being presented to a larger audience increases as interaction increases. Therefore, companies need to create content that can both keep their current customers interested and spread to new people.

1.3.8. The exciting potential dimension of AI enabled and data driven Social Media Content and Consumer Engagement

The environment of social media content and consumer engagement will alter as technology and consumer behaviour continue to develop and adapt. Some future thoughts and developments are as follows:

- **Video Dominance:** Unleashing the Power of Video Marketing for Unparalleled Brand Success

As a content marketing manager, it's evident that video content is poised to maintain its upward trajectory in terms of popularity. In the ever-evolving digital landscape, we can expect to witness a significant rise in the popularity and prevalence of live streaming, short-form videos, and interactive experiences. These dynamic and engaging forms of content consumption are set to revolutionise the way we connect, entertain, and educate ourselves. Live streaming, with its real-time nature, allows individuals and brands to connect with their audience on a deeper level. Whether it's a product launch, a behind-the-scenes glimpse, or a live event, this immersive medium creates

□ **Dominance in Video:**

Videos are likely to keep getting more and more common. More and more people will use live streaming, short movies, and interactive encounters.

□ **Unlocking the Potential of Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR):**

A Revolutionary Experience Awaits! In today's fast-paced digital landscape, technology continues to push boundaries and reshape the way we interact with the world around us. Two groundbreaking innovations that have captured the imagination of both consumers and businesses alike are Augmented Reality (AR)

Discover the transformative power of AR and VR technologies, as they pave the way for unparalleled immersive experiences. These cutting-edge advancements are revolutionising the way consumers interact with brands, opening up a world of endless possibilities. Prepare to be captivated as you embark on a journey that will redefine your perception of engagement and take your brand experience to unprecedented heights. Get ready to embrace the future of consumer-brand interactions with AR and VR technologies.

□ **Addressing Privacy Concerns in the Digital Age: Ensuring Your Data Remains Secure** In today's interconnected world, privacy concerns have become a pressing

In today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, the issue of data privacy has emerged as a paramount concern for businesses across industries. As consumers become increasingly aware of the potential risks associated with sharing their personal information, it is imperative for companies to strike a delicate balance between delivering personalised content and respecting consumer privacy and consent. The era of one-size-fits-all marketing strategies is long gone. Modern consumers expect tailored experiences that cater to their unique preferences and needs. However, this heightened demand for personalised content must be met with a deep commitment to safeguarding the privacy of individuals. To navigate this complex terrain, businesses must adopt a proactive approach that prioritises transparency and consent. By clearly communicating their data collection and usage practises, companies can foster trust and empower consumers to make informed decisions about sharing their personal information. Moreover, implementing robust security measures and adhering to stringent data protection regulations are crucial

□ **Unlocking the Power of AI-Powered Personalization for Unparalleled Customer Experiences**

In today's hyper-connected digital landscape, businesses are constantly seeking innovative methods of engaging customers. As we look ahead to the future of content marketing, it becomes increasingly evident that artificial intelligence (AI) will undoubtedly take centre stage. With its immense potential, AI is set to revolutionise the way we tailor content to individual preferences, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of personalization strategies. The integration of AI into content marketing opens up a world of possibilities. By leveraging advanced algorithms and machine learning capabilities, AI can analyse vast amounts of data to gain deep insights into consumer behaviour, preferences, and interests. This invaluable information allows marketers to create highly personalised content that resonates with each individual on a deeper level. Gone are the days of generic, one-size-fits-all content. With AI-driven personalization, brands can deliver tailored experiences that cater to the unique needs and desires of their target audience.

□ **Unlocking the Power of Fleeting Moments in the Digital Age: Ephemeral content as a powerful tool**

In today's fast-paced digital landscape, it's no surprise that stories and disappearing content continue to captivate audiences across various platforms. These ephemeral features provide a unique and thrilling experience, offering a sense of urgency and exclusivity that keeps users coming back for more. By embracing this trend, brands can tap into the power of storytelling and create a genuine connection with their target audience. So, if you're looking to stay ahead of the curve and engage your customers in a dynamic way, incorporating stories and disappearing content into your marketing strategy is a must. Get ready to captivate, excite, and leave a lasting impression on your customers to engage with your products/services, brands or stores.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The digital material is based on research conducted after the fact as well as up-to-the-minute observations from the dynamic field of business and digital marketing. It also discusses informational facets of assistants that are often accessible via search engine prompts. The writers have conducted an in-depth analysis of a broad variety of sources, such as publications, research papers, newspapers, magazines, numerous websites, and material found online. A few investigate papers and articles offer in-depth experiences into the domain of Online Showcasing. The following are the conclusions derived from the writing, which explore the latest trends, strategies, and best practises that are shaping the digital landscape. These would uncover valuable insights and gain a competitive edge in this ever-evolving domain. The key takeaways from the content can be summarised as follows:

2.1 Defining Social Media Influencers

Simply put, the term "web marketing" refers to the process of achieving marketing goals via the use of digital technology. (Chaffey et al., 2009). The goal of digital marketing is to better understand and meet the demands of customers, thus businesses are increasingly turning to digital technology to support their marketing efforts. (Chaffey, 2013). In the realm of social media, those who have amassed a sizable fan base by their own efforts are referred to as "social media influencers." (Evans et al. 2017; De Veirman, Cauberghe, and Hudders 2017; Jin and Phua 2014). Compared to conventional celebrities, consumers are more likely to put their faith in social media influencers, according to recent studies. (Grave 2017).

Self-influencer image congruence serves as a motivating framework to influence consumers' appraisal of branded messaging, engagement with brand content on social media, and brand purchase intentions in the same way (Shan, Y., Chen, K. J., & Lin, J. S. (2020). Everyday Internet users who amass a sizable online following through the written and visual narration of their lives and ways of living, who interact with that audience in both virtual and real-world settings, and who monetize their audiences through the integration of 'advertorials' into their online content are known as "influencers" (Abidin, C. 2015). In terms of delivering results and measuring the return on investment for advertising expenditures, digital marketing emerges as a more cost-effective method (Pepelnjak, 2008). Sundermann and Raabe (2019) utilised an approach based on strategic communication. Factors including influencer kind, source reputation, and ad content features were all mentioned as important considerations for influencer marketing communication. Parasocial interactions and connections, sponsorship,

authenticity, engagement, and influence were emphasised as the primary research streams in the field of social media influencer marketing (Joshi, Y., Lim, W. M., Jagani, K., & Kumar, S. 2023)

The advent of digital and social media platforms has significantly transformed the landscape of marketing. (Kozinets et al. 2010). Recent studies have begun to investigate the significance of influencers' content-related indicators for predicting online opinion leadership. (Djafarova & Rushworth, 2017; Ki & Kim, 2019). This research adds to the business and marketing literature by investigating the interplay between an individual's sense of identity and their purchasing habits in relation to social media communication, brand awareness, and fashion (Schivinski, B., Pontes, N., Czarnecka, B., Mao, W., De Vita, J., & Stavropoulos, V., 2022)

2.2 Who is a Social Media Influencer

Regular individuals with specialised expertise who then go on to gain fame and fortune as content producers on social media are known as "social media influencers" (Lou, C., & Yuan, S. (2019). The word "influencer" was coined from the idea of opinion leaders in the offline world, but in the context of the internet, where certain people may wield a great deal of sway through their network of friends and acquaintances (Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C., & Ibáñez-Sánchez, S. 2018).

Influencers are defined by their desire to become well-known and influential through their content creation and sharing activities on social media. (Abidin, C 2016)

Influencers are characterised by their aspiration to attain prominence and exert influence by means of their efforts in content generation and dissemination on social media platforms. (Pedroni, M 2016). There is no denying the growing significance of SMI as brand advocates on social media. To the best of our knowledge, no research have used preconceptions based on physical appearance to assess how others see SMI's attractiveness, trustworthiness, or skill.(Cheung, M. L., Leung, W. K., Yang, M. X., Koay, K. Y., & Chang, M. K., 2022)

According to Li (2011) People are said to be under the influence of information when they accept the information provided by others as reliable proof of the world around them and then modify their actions as a result of this information. The influence of social media communication on consumer inclinations to buy increases or decreases with the degree to which its recipients are true to themselves (Schivinski, B., Pontes, N., Czarnecka, B., Mao, W., De Vita, J., & Stavropoulos, V., 2022) The audience's assessment of the communication's quality is correlated with how credible they find the information's source to be. (Sokolova & Kefi, 2020). When consumers value the information, they get as increasing their understanding beyond that of their peer groups, they are also influenced by it. (Kelman,H C 2006). The confidence that followers have in influencers' sponsored content and the actions they are willing to take are both influenced favourably by the material's informational value. If the information is perceived as useful by the audience, the message is more likely to be accepted and internalised (Lou & Yuan, 2019).

2.3 Content Characteristics – effectiveness, engagement, design

According to Cheung, M. L., Leung, W. K., Aw, E. C. X., & Koay, K. Y. (2022) Parasocial connection and wishful identification development and subsequent behavioural engagement may be influenced by content features including information, design, and technological quality and inventiveness (COBRAs).

Marketing strategies that focus on the creation and distribution of information in the hopes that it will attract and retain customers is known as "content marketing." This has seen a rise in popularity during the past few years. (De Mers 2014) while more than half of all marketers saying they plan to boost their usage of content marketing during the next few years to come. (Pulizzi and Handley 2014). User Generated Content (user contributed content) has a favourable and statistically significant impact on users' inclinations to interact with Instagram (Davicik, N. S., Langaro, D., Jevons, C., & Nascimento, R., 2022). Sharing information, rather than searching for it, is a defining feature of social media. This includes both the dissemination of information (posting) and its consumption (selected reading, forwarding, commenting, connecting, and like). More work has been put into studying the 'providing' side of information sharing than the 'receiving' side (Chung, N., Han, H., & Koo, C. (2015). Brands may reap benefits from the consumption and sharing of audience-created content if they effectively advertise it. The study also shed light on how to acquire CM competence with little wasted time and money (Ho, J., Pang, C. and Choy, C., 2020)

Social media managers rely heavily on customers interacting with their brands online, but there has been a dearth of research into what motivates people to follow premium companies on social media. perceptions of content's usefulness (related to brands, posts, and celebrities), (Bazi, S., Filieri, R., & Gorton, M., 2020). Advertisements on social networking sites (SNSs) raise brand awareness and consumer interest in a business's products or services, and they also aim to improve the efficiency of their content (Mohamed, T. I., Osman, N. A. Q., & Badr, A. M. N. A., 2022). Design qualities (visual appeal and musicality), scenario features (creativity and entertainment value), and structure (unity and conciseness) as the three overarching factors to classify the material (Kim, C., Oh, E., & Shin, N, 2010)

2.4 Digital Content

Businesses have progressively adopted the use of digital content for marketing as well as a specialised end product (Tsai, H., Lee, H., and Yu, H. 2008). Digital material must be viewed as more than just a collection of discrete elements like text, music, photos, and video (Benlian, A. and Hess, T 2007). Traditional pillars of success like content and production know-how are seen as less important by viewers (Michael T. Lee, Carol Theokary 2021). Design may be defined by the aesthetic appeal of visuals and the musicality of sound. The higher the value and flow of digital material, the better the artistic and visual impact. Musicality refers to the quality of sound effects and background music, both of which have a significant impact on how viewers react to digital material. Musicality has a significant impact on the value and flow of digital material. (Sullivan, B., Ware, C., and Plumlee, M. 2006). Information recombination, accessibility, navigation engagement, speed, and almost no marginal cost are some of the hallmarks of digital material (Koiso-Kanttila, N., 2004)

2.5 Customer Engagement

Since 2010, a lot of studies have looked into what motivates consumers to engage themselves based on the social media influence and content. However, those fields have become disorganised due to a lack of agreement on how to define their constructs. Different

gratifications (information seeking, amusement, reward, and contact) may be used to predict consumer-influencer engagement behaviours, and these behaviours have a substantial beneficial effect on customer engagement with endorsed businesses (Cheung, M. L., Leung, W. K., Yang, M. X., Koay, K. Y., & Chang, M. K., 2022). Engagement rates were increased by high-quality images and the presence of the athlete's teammates, and decreased by the use of hashtags (Doyle, J. P., Su, Y., & Kunkel, T., 2022). Agrawal, S. R., & Mittal, D, 2022 used a four-factor model based on consumer engagement content accessible and online product review videos, the study investigates novel insights for forecasting buy intents of potential customers. (Casalo, L. V., Flavian, C., Guinalú, M., & Ekinci, , 2015) discuss on how star ratings on social media affect people's interest in engaging with companies products/brands. Customer attitude towards their digital participation can be influenced by social media engagement campaigns that accompany customer-experience interaction events. (Meire, Matthijs; Hewett, Kelly et al 2019). Marketing using electronic mail utilising visual cues such as...improved customer engagement, brand loyalty, and brand profitability may be achieved by the strategic use of emojis to pique the interest of an audience, spark conversation, forge connections, and spread the word (Valenzuela-Gálvez, E. S., Garrido-Morgado, A., & González-Benito, Ó. 2023). The distinct ways in which consumers interact with brand posts are theorised to be related to a typology of fourteen content characteristics spanning various aspects of what companies say and how they say it. The most influential drivers of engagement are those that are related to the ability to persuade. In contrast to the effectiveness of persuasive content qualities in traditional marketing communications, they are found to have the opposite effect in the social media setting. This study elucidates consumers' cognitive processes when they engage with branded material on social media and suggests ways in which content might be optimised for brand engagement (Stephen, A. T., Sciandra, M., & Inman, J., 2015)

2.6 Online Content & Review Ratings

Virality is affected by people's feelings. The findings suggest that upbeat material spreads more easily than negative pieces. Viral content is more likely to elicit strong positive (awe) or negative (anger, anxiety) feelings. Less popular is material that elicits low-arousal feelings like melancholy (Berger, J., & Milkman, K. L., 2012)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive assessment of the literature that is currently accessible was carried out, and research articles published over the past 15 years that focus on social media platforms, social media influencers, content characteristics, customer engagement, online content review ratings, and how these things cause consumer engagement were investigated. A great number of researchers have investigated a variety of factors associated with purchase intention, developing customer loyalty to a brand, improving the efficiency and efficacy of landing pages, doing research on search engine optimisation and search engine marketing, assessing levels of consumer trust, and measuring the effectiveness of sales performance in relation to content. A limited number of research papers have investigated the effect of content on customer engagement across social media platforms. The authors have, at long last, begun the process of attempting to build a few conceptual frameworks based on the literature gaps that were uncovered as a result of the study.

3.1 Research Gaps identified

Some of the gaps identified in this review paper are ...

- Limited studies were conducted on social media influence, customer demographics, various SM Platforms, content characteristics that engage consumer engagement, (Meire, Matthijs, Hewett, Kelly; Ballings, Michel; Kumar V.; Van den Poel, Dirk)
- Social media influence, social media platforms, social media vis-à-vis costs and metrics,
- Customer reviews, Customer experience, UX
- Content research variables like – characteristics, value, effectiveness, information, effectiveness, cost, appeal, design, structure,
- User generated content and customer engagement

3.2 Research Objectives

1. To develop a tentative conceptual framework of research in the areas mentioned in the gap analysis.
2. To examine the literature and models studied by various researchers in social media influence, social media channels, demographic data of consumers, customer engagement
3. To explore digital consumer engagement through content enrichment, social media influence for a product/ brand or store

4. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF RESEARCH

Based on the gaps identified in this review of pertinent literature a few frameworks have been developed, that may help enthusiast researchers to probe in further into research on the above-mentioned areas.

Conceptual framework 1 (Source: developed by the authors based on their study of pertinent literature)

Conceptual framework 2 (Source: developed by the authors based on their study of pertinent literature)

Conceptual framework 3 (Source: developed by the authors based on their study of pertinent literature)

5. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF STUDY

India is undergoing a major transformation in which everything is becoming digitised. Customers are seeking and researching on the internet for the greatest pricing from suppliers all across India in comparison to Traditional techniques are the tried-and-true ways of accomplishing things. The term "conventional methods" refers to the most prevalent and widely recognised approaches to tasks. On these sites, users will do online purchasing. This indicates that if someone considers purchasing services on social networking sites to be useful and easy to use, they are more likely to purchase items online through these sites. Platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram are becoming popular tools for individuals to use while searching for and purchasing items on the internet. Marketing and purchasing choices are highly reliant on social media sites such as Facebook, Twitter, Myspace, and LinkedIn. They are also utilised for product and service promotion.

Influencer marketing is a powerful strategy that involves partnering with prominent social media personalities who boast a substantial following. By leveraging their influence, businesses can effectively promote their products or services to a wider audience. Content automation is a cutting-edge approach that leverages sophisticated software to streamline the creation and dissemination of content. By harnessing the power of automation, businesses can efficiently generate and distribute high-quality content across various platforms. This innovative technique eliminates the need for manual content creation, saving valuable time and resources. With content automation, organisations can enhance their content marketing strategies, engage their target audience, and drive meaningful results.

In a study conducted by Chu in 2011, compelling evidence was discovered that further solidifies the undeniable link between Facebook groups and brand affinity. This research sheds light on the immense potential that lies within these online communities, showcasing their ability to foster meaningful connections and drive brand engagement. With this valuable insight, marketers can now leverage the power of Facebook groups to cultivate a loyal customer base and propel their brands to new heights. Discover the power of active engagement, delve into the intriguing dynamics of consumer response to commercials, and explore the intricate realm of sharing personal information and opinions within and beyond the realms of Facebook groups.

Growing social media has changed the way businesses communicate with their clients. Social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn have evolved into effective tools for engaging audiences and advertising goods and services. This article delves into the complex link between social media content and consumer interaction, putting light on the tactics and best practises that may assist businesses in navigating this ever-changing digital landscape.

Customer Engagement and the Role of Social Media Content: Social media content is crucial in creating client engagement. It acts as a link between businesses and their customers in the digital arena. Effective social media content entails more than simply publishing captivating headlines and eye-catching pictures; it also entails engaging in meaningful discussions with the target audience.

Relevance and Personalization of Social Media Content: Customer engagement on social media may be boosted in part by providing material that is relevant to their interests. According to studies cited by Smith and Johnson (2018), personalised content that caters to individuals'

specific interests and preferences can considerably increase participation. Consumers are more inclined to take action in response to material they see as relevant to them personally.

The effect of the contents' emotional appeal: Customer involvement relies heavily on appealing to their emotions. Vargas et al. (2019) found that content that elicits positive emotions like delight, surprise, or empathy can increase engagement. Businesses may interact with their target market on a more personal level by using storytelling, user-generated material, and client testimonials.

The Role of Different Forms of Content on User Interest: There is a wide range in the impact on consumer engagement from various forms of social media material. If you want to create a well-rounded content strategy, you need to know the advantages and disadvantages of each content category.

Visual Content, such as photos and movies, is particularly successful in catching the audience's attention. According to the findings of Chang and Wu (2020), postings that include images are more likely to be interacted with than those that are just textual. Businesses should prioritise the production of content that is both aesthetically pleasing and effective in conveying their message.

User-generated content (UGC), or material made by a brand's consumers or followers, may be used effectively to increase credibility and trust. Since user-generated content (UGC) reflects the actual experiences of delighted consumers, it typically leads to better engagement rates, as studied by Anderson et al. (2017). Encouraging consumers to share their tales and experiences may enhance engagement and brand loyalty.

Interactive material in the content: Audience engagement may be increased with the use of interactive material like polls, quizzes, and competitions. According to the findings of Chen and Wang (2019), postings that encourage participation and discussion generate more comments and shares. In order to maintain the interest of their social media followers, businesses should use interactive features.

When and how often content is uploaded: The timing and frequency of material distribution can have a major effect on reader participation. Kumar and Ramesh's (2018) study shows that each social media platform has its own prime hour for sharing content. Putting up content when your intended readers are most likely to see it, for instance, has been shown to increase interaction. In addition, posts should be made often enough to maintain interest without becoming annoyingly frequent. Regular updates keep readers interested over time (Kumar & Ramesh, 2018).

Creating Community Connection and Promoting Participation: There's more to social media than just a place to share ads; it's also a place to make connections with like-minded people. Participating in conversations, reacting to comments, and addressing customer problems in a timely manner all help businesses establish a sense of belonging and engagement (Smith and Johnson, 2018).⁵

Measuring and Analyzing Engagement Metrics: To optimize customer engagement, it's crucial to measure and analyze relevant metrics. Tools like Google Analytics, social media analytics platforms, and customer relationship management (CRM) software can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of social media content.

Key Metrics and Indicators: Likes, shares, comments, CTR, and conversion rates are all important indicators of success. Using these KPIs, organisations may evaluate how well their social media efforts are fostering client interaction and leading to desired action.

A/B Testing: By using A/B testing, companies may evaluate how several versions of their content perform. A company's content strategy may be honed for more engagement via testing different aspects including headlines, images, and publishing schedules (Chen and Wang, 2019).

Sentiment Analysis: Companies can benefit from analysing the sentiment of social media consumer interactions with the use of sentiment analysis tools. Businesses may better serve their customers' needs and address their concerns by monitoring consumer feedback (Vargas et al., 2019).

Ethical Issues and Implementation challenges: There are many advantages to using social media to interact with customers, but there are also risks to be aware of. Organisations need to ethically handle problems including cyberbullying, data breaches, and the propagation of disinformation (Chang and Wu, 2020).

6. CONCLUSION

It is clear and evident that Companies' product/services/brands or stores provide several advantages that meet the demands of visitors/customers and encourage them from trying to becoming their advocates

In today's ever-evolving marketing landscape, it's crucial for businesses to recognise the undeniable connection between social media content and customer engagement. These two elements go hand in hand, forming the backbone of successful marketing strategies. By leveraging the power of social media platforms, businesses can effectively engage with their target audience and foster meaningful connections that drive brand loyalty and ultimately, business growth. Let's explore the symbiotic relationship between social media content and customer engagement, and how businesses can harness their combined potential to achieve marketing success. In order to thrive in today's ever-evolving business environment, it is imperative for companies to craft compelling and relatable content that strikes an emotional chord with their audience. By leveraging a diverse range of content formats, businesses can effectively capture the attention of their target market and keep them engaged. Furthermore, adopting data-driven strategies allows organisations to fine-tune their content to maximise audience interaction and achieve optimal results. Embracing these practises is key to achieving success in this fast-paced and competitive landscape. In today's digital landscape, businesses have a unique opportunity to leverage the immense power of social media to cultivate authentic communities, track essential metrics, and navigate ethical considerations. By adopting these strategic approaches, companies can establish meaningful connections with their customers, fostering loyalty and propelling growth in the ever-evolving digital age.

7. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Based on our findings, we can also claim that despite our best efforts, there are certain limits to the frameworks we intended to create for use by enthusiastic researchers. Some of these might be particularly pointed: -

- The variables described in the conceptual frameworks need to be supported, justified, and drawn importance to using relevant theories, models, and testing the model fit with proper statistical tools and procedures.
- The validity and suitability of the frameworks for the study at hand must be verified.
- Time is another restriction that was encountered by the Authors
- Expenses and extrapolating results from the reviews the writers looked at might potentially be a major caveat.

8. SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The following below mentioned research points can serve as a starting point for conducting in-depth studies and analyses on the influence of social media content on consumer engagement. Researchers can choose specific aspects that align with their interests and objectives to contribute to the growing body of knowledge in this field.

- Explore the effects of various forms of content on customer interaction, including but not limited to emojis, text, reviews, blogs, user-generated material, photos, videos, and infographics.
- What influences consumer interaction with social media material, and when: the influencer's role, the social media platform, the content's cost, and the content's timeliness.
- Compare the levels of customer involvement prompted by personalised and generic information and report your findings.
- Examine the effect that reviews' emotional tone has on reader participation.
- Aesthetics in terms of presentation, including content length, hashtag usage, content attractiveness, and user participation.
- Determine how user-generated content influences interaction with your brand's target audience.
- Find out if and how different demographics affect people's interest in social media posts.
- Consider the impact of cultural norms on users' propensity to interact with material shared on social media platforms.
- Examine the connection between the reliability of content providers and reader participation.

- Determine what makes material go viral and how that affects audience participation.
- Examine the role of social media material in the customer's decision-making process, from initial exposure through post-purchase follow-up.
- Examine the effect that worries about sharing personal information has on people's interest in sharing material on social media.

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